

Effect of Substituents on the Relative Stabilities of Fe(III) Complexes of Substituted Salicylic Acids

M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

The stability constants of Fe(III) complexes of salicylic acid (SA) and ten of its substituted derivatives were determined at constant ionic strength using spectrophotometric measurements. Fe(III)-SA system was taken as a reference for comparing the difference in the acid dissociation constants (ΔpK) and stability constant values ($\Delta \log K$). A parallelism is observed, though the magnitude of $\Delta \log K$ is less than ΔpK . While the substitution of an electron donor group increases the stability constant, it decreases the value of the apparent equilibrium constant. Similarly, the electron withdrawing groups have opposite effect on these two parameters. A hypsochromic shift in the absorption maximum (λ_{max}) of 1 : 1 complex is observed when an electron withdrawing group is substituted in the nucleus of the reference ligand, whereas other groups (or an atom like Hg) give a bathochromic shift. However, exact correlation between $\Delta \lambda_{max}$ and $\Delta \log K$ or ΔpK was not observed.

IRON(III), due to its pronounced affinity for ligands containing oxygen, forms several coloured complexes with salicylic acids¹⁻¹⁵. Thus, salicylic acid and sulphosalicylic acid have extensively been used as colorimetric reagent¹⁶⁻¹⁸ for iron(III). Similar to Fe(III)-phenol complexes¹⁹⁻²⁰, the colour of Fe(III)-salicylates depends on the various substituent groups attached to salicylates. The substitution effect influences the dissociation constants²¹ and consequently the metal ligand stability constants. Hence, it was thought of interest to study the influence of substitution on the stability constants and on the absorption spectra of Fe(III)-salicylates. For this purpose, salicylic acid and ten of its substituted derivatives were chosen as ligands.

Experimental

Methods :

Reagent grade samples of the following salicylic acids were employed : (i) 2-Hydroxy benzoic acid (SA), (B.D.H.), (ii) 2-Hydroxy 3-methyl benzoic acid (oCA), (B.D.H.), (iii) 2-Hydroxy 4-methyl benzoic acid (mCA), (K and K Lab), (iv) 2-Hydroxy 5-methyl benzoic acid (pCA), (K and K Lab), (v) 2-Hydroxy 5-nitro benzoic acid (NSA), (Fluka), (vi) 2-Hydroxy 5-chloro benzoic acid (CSA), (Fluka), (vii) 2-Hydroxy 5-sulpho benzoic acid (SSA), (E. Merck), (viii) 2-Hydroxy 3-methyl 5-sulpho benzoic acid (SoCA), (ix) 2-Hydroxy 4-methyl 5-sulpho benzoic acid (SmCA), (x) 2-Hydroxy 3-sulpho 5-methyl benzoic acid (SpCA) and (xi) 2-Hydroxy 3-mercury 5-sulpho benzoic acid (HgSSA). The acids (viii) to (xi) were prepared as described earlier²².

All the acids were purified by several recrystallizations before use. Aqueous solutions were prepared by direct weighing, using CO₂-free water. A stock solution of ferric chloride in dilute HClO₄

was prepared and standardised titrimetrically against standard dichromate solution. CO₂-free NaOH and HClO₄ solutions were used for bringing the pH at the desired value. Solutions of acids and alkalis were standardised by conventional titrimetric methods. NaClO₄ was used as a background electrolyte.

Procedure :

In the pH range 1-3.5, the reaction between Fe(III) ion and salicylic acids (H₂L) takes place as follows :

Charges are omitted for simplicity.

At constant pH, the apparent equilibrium constant can be expressed as :

$$K'_1 = \frac{[\text{FeL}]}{(\text{Fe}^\circ - [\text{FeL}])(\text{L}^\circ - [\text{FeL}])} \quad \dots (2)$$

Fe^o and L^o being the initial concentration of iron(III) and ligand, respectively.

The stability constant is defined as

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{FeL}]}{[\text{F}][\text{L}]} = K'_1 \phi \quad \dots (3)$$

where

$$\phi = 1 + \frac{[\text{H}]}{K_2^H} + \frac{[\text{H}]^2}{K_1^H K_2^H} \quad \dots (4)$$

K₁^H and K₂^H are the dissociation constants (concentration quotient) of ligand for carboxyl and phenolic groups, respectively. Knowing the values of K₁^H, K₂^H and [H], K₁ can be calculated from equation (3) at a particular ionic strength.

To find out K₁^H at a definite pH value (2.35 ± 0.05), the molar absorptivity, ε, for ML species at

λ_{max} was determined by elimination method²³. Taking average value of ϵ , K'_1 was calculated at ionic strength of 0.1 from

$$K'_1 = \frac{\epsilon A}{(\epsilon M^0 - A)(\epsilon L^0 - A)} \quad \dots (5)$$

where A is absorbance value at λ_{max} .

Using K'_1 and K''_2 at $I=0.1$, determined by the method as described earlier²¹, $\log K_1$ was calculated. The relevant data of each system are summarised in Table 1.

0.1, the pH of the solution was varied in the range 1.4-3.2 by adding different amounts of HClO₄ and K_1 values were determined. It is observed that there is no appreciable change in K_1 values in the pH range 1.4-2.0, but above pH 2.0, the value decreases, probably due to the hydrolysis of the uncomplexed Fe(III). The effect due to hydrolysis can be accounted for by multiplying the right hand side of equation (3) by the correction factor²⁴ $(1 + K_h/[H])$, where K_h is the first stage hydrolysis constant for Fe(III), the value²⁵ of K_h being 2.34×10^{-3} at $I=0.1$. Consistency is then observed in

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANT OF Fe(III)-COMPLEX AT IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.1

Ligand	pK_1^H	pK_2^H	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	$\log K'_1$	$\log K_1$	ΔpK	$\Delta \log K'_1$	$\Delta \log K_1$	$\Delta \lambda_{max}$
SA	2.81	13.24	530	1660	4.70	16.19 (16.37)*	—	—	—	—
oCA	2.84	14.14	556	1660	4.34	16.75 (16.93)	-0.93	+0.36	-0.56	-26
mCA	2.94	13.54	534	1663	4.61	16.49 (16.67)	-0.43	+0.09	-0.30	-04
pCA	2.87	13.74	560	1852	4.62	16.05 (16.83)	-0.56	+0.08	-0.46	-30
NSA	1.90	9.89	496	2097	5.09	12.76 (12.94)	+4.26	-0.39	+3.43	+34
CSA	2.43	12.50	536	1909	4.76	15.25 (15.43)	+1.12	-0.06	+0.94	+06
SSA	2.44	11.90	506	1931	5.00	14.60 (14.78)	+1.71	-0.30	+1.59	+24
SoCA	2.54	12.58	530	2116	4.70	15.34 (15.52)	+0.93	0.0	+0.85	0
SmCA	2.67	12.33	510	2177	4.76	15.23 (15.41)	+1.05	-0.06	+0.96	+20
SpCA	2.52	13.47	546	2213	4.83	16.34 (16.52)	+0.06	-0.13	-0.15	-16
HgSSA	2.43	12.03	514	2038	5.08	15.10 (15.28)	+1.59	-0.38	+1.09	+16

*Values within parentheses include correction factor for hydrolysis of Fe(III)

At higher pH values (above 3.5), higher species of the complex are formed as evident from the study of isosbestic points on absorption spectra at different pH values. The formation of higher species takes place as follows:

At pH 4 and above, considerable hydrolysis of Fe(III) takes place and consequently the stability constant values for higher species were not determined.

All pH measurements were made with a Universal pH meter (Redelkis OP-204, Hungary) with glass and calomel electrodes. The absorption spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 UV-Vis or SF-4 USSR spectrophotometers. Measurements were done at room temperature at $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Results and Discussions

To study the effect of pH on the stability constant of ML species, solutions of Fe(III) ion and the ligand were prepared by mixing them in a 1 : 1 ratio. While the ionic strength was maintained at

the values of K_1 (the corrected values are shown within the parenthesis in Table 1).

For examining the effect of substitution, Fe(III)-SA system was taken as reference for comparison with other systems. The difference in the values of pK_1^H , K_2^H , $\log K'_1$, $\log K_1$ and λ_{max} were expressed as ΔpK , $\Delta \log K'_1$, $\Delta \log K_1$ and $\Delta \lambda$, respectively (Table 1). It is noted that the sign (+ or -) of pK and the corresponding $\Delta \log K_1$ is identical. However, $\Delta \log K_1$ value is smaller in magnitude when compared to ΔpK . A linear plot of $\log K_1$ vs pK_1^H , K_2^H with a positive slope (< 1) is obtained. However, a small departure is observed in the case of Fe(III)-SpCA systems.

Equation (3) can be written as :

$$\log K_1 = \log K'_1 + \log \phi \quad \dots (8)$$

ϕ is a function of K_1^H and K_2^H and hence at a particular pH the value of $\log \phi$ increases with the increase in pK_1^H , K_2^H value. The value of $\log K'_1$, however, decreases with the increase in pK_1^H , K_2^H . Due to this opposing influence, the net increase (or decrease) in $\log K_1$ value is significantly less than that of ΔpK_1^H , K_2^H .

In equilibrium (1), both hydrogen as well as the metal compete for L. If the dissociation constant is large (smaller value of $pK_1^H K_2^H$), [L] available for Fe(III) to form the complex is also more. Consequently at a given pH, $\log K_1$ is higher. $\log K_1$ not only indicates the stability of the complex, but includes the term which is competitive with (and appreciably so at lower pH) complex formation, whereas $\log K_1$ is proportional to the free energy change for the reaction $M+L=ML$.

In the absorption spectra studies of 1 : 1 complex, with SA as the reference ligand, the following substitution effects can be noted.

Hypsochromic shift : $-\text{NO}_2, -\text{SO}_3\text{H}$

Bathochromic shift : $-\text{CH}_3, -\text{Hg}, -\text{Cl}$

Similar observations were made by Ackerman and Hesse²⁰ in the case of Fe(III)-phenol complexes. However, the extent of the effect decreases with the increasing number of substituents. For example, the substitution of methyl group in *meta* position shifts the λ_{max} of Fe(III)-phenol complex²⁰ by 15 nm, while in the case of Fe(III)-SA complex it is only 4 nm.

Since the electron acceptor groups shift the λ_{max} to shorter wavelengths and electron donating groups to longer wavelengths, an apparent correlation between λ_{max} and stability constant is expected. Table 1 also shows that $\Delta\lambda$ and $\Delta\log K_1$ values have the same sign. But in the case of Fe(III)-phenol complexes the stability has been regarded as the function of the electron density of phenolate oxygen while the λ_{max} depends on the difference in energy between anion and radical²⁰. Similar may be the case with Fe(III)-salicylates and hence any exact correlation between λ_{max} and stability constant is unlikely. This is obvious from the fact that CH_3 group acts as the strongest donor at *ortho* position while considering the pK_2^H and $\log K_1$ values but the λ_{max} of Fe(III)-pCA complex is more than that of Fe(III)-oCA complex. Further the λ_{max} of Fe(III)-SA complex and Fe(III)-SoCA complex is the same but their stability constants differ considerably.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Professor W. A. E. McBryde, Department of Chemistry, University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada for valuable suggestions.

References

1. A. K. BABKO, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1945, 15, 745, 748.
2. R. T. FOLEY and R. C. ANDERSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195; 1950, 72, 5609.
3. A. AGREN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 266, 1059; 1955, 9, 39.
4. A. AGREN, *Svensk. Kem. Tidskr.*, 1956, 68, 181, 185, 189.
5. D. D. PERRIN, *Nature*, 1958, 182, 74.
6. S. C. TRIPATHI and S. PRAKASH, *Z. Phy. Chem.*, 1958, 204, 326.
7. J. C. COLLECTER, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1960, 5, 415.
8. K. J. DIVEKAR, *J. Sci. Ind. Research*, 1962, 21B, 309.
9. S. S. KATIYAR and V. B. S. CHAUHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 94.
10. Z. L. ERNST and J. MENASHI, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 1794.
11. M. V. PARK, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 816.
12. K. OGAWA and M. TOBE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1966, 39, 223, 227.
13. S. S. KATIYAR and V. B. S. CHAUHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 796.
14. W. A. E. MCBRYDE, J. L. ROHR, J. S. PENCINER and J. A. PAGE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, 48, 2574.
15. M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, 38, 569.
16. R. O. SCOTT, *Analyst*, 1941, 66, 142.
17. E. B. SANDEL, "Colorimetric Determination of Trace Metals", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1959.
18. Z. MARCZENKO, "Spectrophotometric Determination of Elements", Ellis Harwood Ltd., Chichester, 1976, p. 313.
19. E. F. W. WESB and W. R. BRODE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1037.
20. V. G. ACKERMANN and D. HESSE, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1970, 375, 77.
21. M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA and R. S. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, 19A, 141.
22. M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA and R. S. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 1126.
23. M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA and R. S. SINGH, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1974, 70, 49.
24. H. S. FRANK and R. L. OSWALT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1321.
25. L. G. SILLEN and A. R. MARTELL, "Stability Constant", Special Publication No. 17, The Chemical Society, London, 1964, p. 54.